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Homogenised formulation for plates with thick constrained viscoelastic core

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Abstract

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The present work analyses the dynamic behaviour of constrained layer damping (CLD) plates with thick viscoelastic layer. The bending modes and transverse response of such plates are obtained by adapting the Kirchhoff–Love thin plate formulation so that it considers the shear stiffness by using a frequency dependent equivalent flexural stiffness.

The developed formulation is introduced in a finite element model and compared to the widely used RKU model and a reference 3D solid model in terms of eigenpairs and amplitude of the response for different boundary conditions.

It is concluded that the developed formulation can substitute either a 3D or RKU model as it requires less computational resources than the former and provides more accurate results than the latter.

Keywords: plate models, constrained layer damping, vibration reduction, fractional damping

1. Introduction

Constrained layer damping (CLD) plates are a common choice as a passive treatment to reduce vibration in structures and prevent structure-borne noise. They are specially used in the automotive [1] and aerospace [2] industry as they help increase passenger comfort.

CLD plates are formed by a base layer, usually metallic, to which a layer of viscoelastic material is glued and that is in turn constrained by a third layer, also commonly metallic. When the plate undergoes bending deformation, the constrained configuration forces the viscoelastic core to deform in shear and, thus, dissipate energy in form of heat [2].

In order to analyse the dynamic behaviour of this type of structures several models have been proposed, either analytical or numerical. The first works were those by Ross [3], Kerwin [4] and Ungar [5] that gave rise to the RKU method,

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14 which is still the standard in the field. In it, the shear strain of the damping
15 layer is related to the bending motion of the plate by defining an equivalent
16 flexural stiffness under the assumption that shear deformation is confined to
17 the core.

18 Regarding analytical models, recently a general theory for thick sandwich
19 structures has been presented [6]. It includes the shear deformations in the host
20 layer so as to make the method applicable to thick structures and, following this
21 idea, develops a model for layered beams, plates and cylindrical plates.

22 When the geometry of the structure is complex it is common to resort to
23 finite element models instead, but, as they are usually based on solids, they are
24 computationally expensive. In order to address this issue two paths have been
25 followed. The firsts consist in proposing specific models for the application,
26 such as [7] in which triangular and rectangular sandwich elements with seven
27 degrees of freedom in each node; [8] in which a three-layer four-node rectangular
28 element with seven degrees of freedom on every node is presented; or [9] in which
29 a nine node isoparametric 2D element is used for the analysis of active-passive
30 composite beams.

31 The second approach consist in developing a homogenised formulation, as
32 done in [10], where a thin plate element that considers the properties of the
33 three layers is derived. This way, a specific model is not needed but, as the
34 effect of shear is not taken into account, it cannot be applied to thick plates.

35 In this work a homogenised formulation for CLD plates based on thin plate
36 theory is presented, so that the need of developing a specific model is avoided,
37 but a frequency dependent equivalent flexural stiffness is proposed so as to
38 consider both the effect of shear and the mechanical properties of the three
39 layers.

40 The work is organised as follows: first, a frequency dependent equivalent
41 flexural stiffness is proposed; then, it is implemented in a finite element model
42 and the eigenpairs and dynamic response for different boundary conditions are
43 computed; finally, the results obtained using the proposed formulation are com-
44 pared to the ones given by both the RKU method and a finite element 3D
45 model.

46 **2. A frequency dependent equivalent flexural stiffness for thick CLD** 47 **plates**

48 For the analysis the CLD plate shown in Figure 1 is considered. It has a
49 size of $A \times B$ and it is formed by a base layer of thickness H_1 , elastic modulus
50 E_1 , density ρ_1 and Poisson's modulus ν_1 ; a viscoelastic layer of thickness H_2 ,
51 modulus E_2 , density ρ_2 and Poisson's modulus ν_2 ; and a constraining layer of
52 thickness H_3 , elastic modulus E_3 , density ρ_3 and Poisson's modulus ν_3 .

53 The objective of the work is to deduce an equivalent flexural stiffness that
54 considers, on the one hand, the three materials and, on the other, the effect of
55 shear stress. Following the example of [11] that extends Oberst's model from
56 beams directly to plates, the method proposed in [12] for thick beams is extended
57 to thick plates.

Figure 1: CLD plate. The dashed line shows the neutral plane.

Taking into account that, according to the classical plate theory [13], the flexural stiffness of an isotropic and homogeneous plate is

$$D = \frac{EH^3}{12(1-\nu^2)} \quad (1)$$

where E , ν and H stand for, respectively, its Young's modulus, Poisson's ratio and thickness, the first step to analyse a CLD plate is to obtain its equivalent flexural stiffness, that is the sum of the flexural stiffnesses of the three layers

$$D_{\text{eq}} = D_1 + D_2 + D_3, \quad (2)$$

D_1 , D_2 and D_3 being the flexural stiffnesses of the base layer, the viscoelastic layer and the constraining layer respectively.

If the limits of the three layers described in Figure 1 are considered, the equivalent flexural stiffness for the plate becomes

$$D_{\text{eq}} = \frac{E_1}{3(1-\nu_1^2)} \int_{-h_n}^{-h_n+H_1} z^2 dz + \frac{E_2}{3(1-\nu_2^2)} \int_{-h_n+H_1}^{-h_n+H_1+H_2} z^2 dz + \frac{E_3}{3(1-\nu_3^2)} \int_{-h_n+H_1+H_2}^{-h_n+H_1+H_2+H_3} z^2 dz \quad (3)$$

where h_n stands for the height of the neutral plane as is given by

$$h_n = \frac{E_1 H_1^2 + E_2 H_2 (2H_1 + H_2) + E_3 H_3 (2H_1 + 2H_2 + H_3)}{2(E_1 H_1 + E_2 H_2 + E_3 H_3)}. \quad (4)$$

Considering the shear and bending behaviours uncoupled as in [14], the resistance to bending can be attributed to the flexural stiffness and the resistance to shear to the shear stiffness alone.

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71 Then, the total shear stiffness is obtained by combining the shear stiffnesses
72 of the three layers as

$$\frac{1}{K_{\text{eq}}} = \frac{1}{K_1} + \frac{1}{K_2} + \frac{1}{K_3} \quad (5)$$

73 where, taking into account the geometry of the plate and considering a
74 quadratic shear stress, K_1 , K_2 and K_3 follow

$$\frac{1}{K_1} = \frac{1}{G_1 B_{\text{eq}}^2} \int_{-h_n}^{-h_n+H_1} \Gamma_1^2 dz, \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{1}{K_2} = \frac{1}{G_2 B_{\text{eq}}^2} \int_{-h_n+H_1}^{-h_n+H_1+H_2} \Gamma_2^2 dz, \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{1}{K_3} = \frac{1}{G_3 B_{\text{eq}}^2} \int_{-h_n+H_1+H_2}^{-h_n+H_1+H_2+H_3} \Gamma_3^2 dz, \quad (8)$$

75 and

$$\Gamma_1 = \frac{E_1 (h_n^2 - z^2)}{2}, \quad (9)$$

$$\Gamma_2 = \frac{E_2 \left((H_1 - h_n)^2 - z^2 \right)}{2} - E_1 H_1 \left(\frac{H_1}{2} - h_n \right), \quad (10)$$

$$\Gamma_3 = \frac{E_3 \left((H_1 + H_2 + H_3 - h_n)^2 - z^2 \right)}{2}. \quad (11)$$

76 The frequency dependent flexural stiffness is defined in analogy to [14] as

$$D(\omega) = \frac{D_{\text{eq}}}{\left(\varphi(\omega) + \sqrt{\varphi(\omega)^2 + 1} \right)^2}, \quad (12)$$

77 where $\varphi(\omega)$ is given by

$$\varphi(\omega) = \frac{\omega \sqrt{D_{\text{eq}} \rho_S}}{2K_{\text{eq}}}, \quad (13)$$

78 $\rho_S = \rho_1 H_1 + \rho_2 H_2 + \rho_3 H_3$ being the mass per unit area of the plate and D_{eq}
79 and K_{eq} the equivalent flexural stiffness and shear stiffness from (3) and (5)
80 respectively.

81 The time dependent counterpart $D(t)$ of this proposed frequency dependent
82 flexural stiffness $D(\omega)$ is introduced in the Kirchhoff–Love equation for thin
83 plates, resulting in

$$D(\omega) \left(\frac{\partial^4 u(x, y, t)}{\partial x^4} + 2 \frac{\partial^4 u(x, y, t)}{\partial x^2 \partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^4 u(x, y, t)}{\partial y^4} \right) + \rho_S \frac{\partial^2 u(x, y, t)}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (14)$$

so that the effect of the shear stress is considered. The variable w that usually denotes the transverse displacement has been substituted throughout the work with u so as to avoid confusion with the frequency ω .

Even though the frequency dependence could be considered a drawback of the proposed formulation, it does not introduce additional intricacy to the modes because damping models for the viscoelastic material in CLD plates are usually frequency dependent.

In addition, the described formulation is still valid if the modulus of the viscoelastic material is complex simply by substituting the modulus E_2 for its complex counterpart E_2^* , that can be or not frequency dependent as well.

It should be noted that, as the formulation is based in a thin plate model it only accounts for bending modes, the ones that are of interest when computing the acoustic response. The same reasoning applies to the static response.

3. Dynamic analysis of a CLD plate using finite elements

The validity of the proposed formulation is checked by implementing it in a finite element model in MATLAB[®]. With this aim, a plate of an area of 0.1 m \times 0.1 m and base and constraining layers of thicknesses $H_1 = H_3 = 1$ mm is considered. In order to test the formulation in the range of thin and thick plates, three different values (1 mm, 5 mm, 10 mm) are selected for the thickness of the viscoelastic layer H_2 .

The properties of the materials are taken from the experimental characterisation of an AISI T 316L stainless steel laminated sheet and a Soundown Vibration Damping Tile material effectuated by Cortés and Elejabarrieta in [15]. This last material is a damping product that is glued to the surface of interest and absorbs vibrational energy in order to reduce structure-borne noise.

The density of the two steel layers is $\rho_1 = 7782$ kg/m³ and their Young's modulus $E_1 = 176.24$ GPa. The viscoelastic layer has a density of $\rho_2 = 1423$ kg/m³ and a complex modulus that follows the four parameter fractional model

$$E_2^*(\omega) = \frac{E_0 + E_\infty (i\omega\tau)^\alpha}{1 + (i\omega\tau)^\alpha} \quad (15)$$

in the frequency domain, where E_0 and E_∞ are the relaxed and unrelaxed moduli respectively, τ is the relaxation time and α is the fractional parameter (see Table 1 for the values). A value of $\nu_1 = \nu_2 = \nu_3 = 0.3$ was considered for the three materials.

E_0 (GPa)	E_∞ (GPa)	τ (μ s)	α
0.353	3.462	314.9	0.873

Table 1: Values of the fractional model

In order to study the dynamic behaviour of the plate two finite element models are developed: a plate model and a solid model. In the first case,

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288 the domain is discretised using four node plate elements with three degrees of
289 freedom in each node: the transverse displacement u and the rotations θ_x and
290 θ_y (Figure 2), the interpolation functions being third order polynomials. The
291 elementary matrices for the element can be found in Appendix A.

Figure 2: Plate element

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303 The second one is a 3D model based on quadratic hexaedra with 27 nodes
304 (see a book on finite elements for the details, e.g., [16]) and it is used as a
305 reference to estimate the accuracy of the proposed formulation in comparison
306 to the RKU method.

307 The 3D model has 6 elements across the thickness, so that each layer has two
308 elements, and 19 nodes in each direction in the plane whereas the plate model
309 has 49 nodes in each direction, this number of nodes being enough to ensure
310 convergence for the first 5 modes.

311 In order to check the validity of the formulation, the eigenpairs of the CLD
312 plate subjected to different boundary conditions and the dynamic response to
313 a uniform pressure are computed using the two finite element models.

313 3.1. Natural frequencies and modal loss factors

314 The eigenpairs of the system satisfy

$$(-\lambda_r^* \mathbf{M} + \mathbf{K}^*(\omega_r)) \phi_r = \mathbf{0} \quad (16)$$

315 where $\omega_r = \text{Re}(\sqrt{\lambda_r^*})$ is the natural frequency for mode r and λ_r^* and ϕ_r are
316 the corresponding eigenvalue and eigenvector for the r -th mode respectively. In
317 the case under study the eigenvalues are complex because the modulus of the
318 viscoelastic material E_2^* is complex. As for the eigenvectors, the viscoelastic
319 layer covers the whole plate, so the damping is proportional and, thus, the
320 eigenvectors are real. In a general case both the eigenvalues and the eigenvectors
321 should be complex.

322 The stiffness matrix varies with frequency, so an iterative method must be
323 used to compute the eigenpairs of the system. The computation starts consider-
324 ing the static stiffness matrix $\mathbf{K}(0)$ in (16) and solving the resulting eigenvalue
325 and eigenvector problem

$$(-\lambda_{r,0} \mathbf{M} + \mathbf{K}(0)) \phi_{r,0} = \mathbf{0} \quad (17)$$

337 from which the natural frequency $\omega_{r,0}$ is obtained taking into account that
 338 $\omega_{r,0} = \sqrt{\lambda_{r,0}}$.

339 Then, the stiffness matrix $\mathbf{K}^*(\omega_{r,0})$, that is now complex, is computed
 340 and the eigenpairs are updated accordingly obtaining $\omega_{r,1}$. If the difference
 341 $|\omega_{r,1} - \omega_{r,0}|$ is less than a given tolerance, the computation stops; if not, the
 342 value $\omega_{r,1}$ is used to update the stiffness matrix again and the cycle is repeated
 343 now obtaining a new value $\omega_{r,2}$. The procedure continues until all the needed
 344 eigenpairs are obtained with the desired tolerance.

345 Because of its formulation, the proposed method implies that for a given fre-
 346 quency ω , the stiffness matrix can be computed from the static stiffness matrix
 347 $\mathbf{K}(0)$ as

$$354 \quad \mathbf{K}^*(\omega) = \frac{D^*(\omega)}{D(0)} \mathbf{K}(0), \quad (18)$$

355 which allows to directly use a traditional thin plate finite element model.

356 In addition, the proposed methodology is able to reproduce the results for
 357 thick beams in [12] and it is coherent with the free layer damping plates when
 358 the thickness of the constraining layer is negligible.

359 With regard to the RKU method, the process described in [4] and, more
 360 recently, in [17] is implemented. For the sake of completion, it is summarised in
 361 Appendix B.

362 In the following sections the values of the natural frequency ω_r and loss
 363 factor η_r for different boundary conditions are presented. Taking into account
 364 that the main application of CLD plates is noise reduction, only the first three
 365 modes are considered, as they are the relevant ones in the acoustic response. For
 366 all the boundary conditions tested (clamped, free, cantilever, simply supported)
 367 the proposed method provides more accurate results than the RKU method in
 368 terms of natural frequencies.

369 As for the loss factor, for the r -th mode it is defined as

$$370 \quad \eta_r = \frac{\text{Im}(\lambda_r^*)}{\text{Re}(\lambda_r^*)}. \quad (19)$$

371 Due to the computational cost that solving the complex eigenvalue problem
 372 requires, traditionally the loss factor has been approximated by the Modal Strain
 373 Energy, that for this application, produces the same results.

374 3.1.1. Clamped in all edges

375 The results for the clamped case for the three values of thickness are shown
 376 in Tables 2-4. Due to the symmetry of the plate, the second mode is double.

377 From the values of natural frequencies and loss factors, the differences be-
 378 tween the two plate models are evident from the thinnest plate, for which the
 379 error is around 25 % for the RKU and the first three modes whereas the proposed
 380 model is able to compute them with a maximum error of 7 %.

381 This divergence increases even more with thickness, the error going up to
 382 47 % for the first mode and the highest thickness if the RKU model is used to
 383 compute it, while the proposed model provides it with an error of 24 %.

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	ω_1 (rad/s)	η_1	ω_2 (rad/s)	η_2	ω_3 (rad/s)	η_3
3D model	14904	0.0592	27703	0.0479	38385	0.0408
Proposed model	15940	0.0457	29617	0.0489	40556	0.0501
RKU model	18413	0.0357	34607	0.0368	47864	0.0364

Table 2: Natural frequencies and loss factors of the clamped plate when $H_2=1$ mm

	ω_1 (rad/s)	η_1	ω_2 (rad/s)	η_2	ω_3 (rad/s)	η_3
3D model	24680	0.0925	41271	0.0663	54480	0.0545
Proposed model	29311	0.0992	47456	0.0939	60339	0.0820
RKU model	34458	0.0787	56558	0.0737	72538	0.0681

Table 3: Natural frequencies and loss factors of the clamped plate when $H_2=5$ mm

	ω_1 (rad/s)	η_1	ω_2 (rad/s)	η_2	ω_3 (rad/s)	η_3
3D model	30018	0.0949	48707	0.0656	63380	0.0539
Proposed model	37282	0.1163	57463	0.1010	71618	0.0917
RKU model	44102	0.0937	68684	0.0820	86097	0.0735

Table 4: Natural frequencies and loss factors of the clamped plate when $H_2=10$ mm

The reason for this deviation is that the RKU model overestimates the natural frequency because it overestimates equivalent stiffness (Figure 3) and underestimates the loss factor [17]. This drawback could be avoided introducing the correction factors such as the ones proposed by Rao [18] for layered beams.

It should be noted that, as the natural frequencies for the three models are different, the values of the loss factor are not directly comparable [12]. In fact, the proposed model gives higher values of loss factor because its stiffness is lower, and, thus, its damping is higher as it is linked to the relationship between the real and imaginary parts of the flexural stiffness [19].

3.1.2. Free

The natural frequencies and loss factors for the free case and the three values of thickness are shown in Tables 5–7.

	ω_1 (rad/s)	η_1	ω_2 (rad/s)	η_2	ω_3 (rad/s)	η_3
3D model	6143	0.0409	9395	0.0194	11440	0.0244
Proposed model	6374	0.0404	9102	0.0425	11118	0.0437
RKU model	7308	0.0323	10457	0.0337	12793	0.0345

Table 5: Natural frequencies and loss factors of the free plate when $H_2=1$ mm

Also in this case the differences between the RKU and the proposed model are clear from the thinnest plate for which the RKU method computes the first mode with an error of 19 %, whereas the proposed model is able to keep the error for the three modes under a 4 %. For the medium plate the error does

Figure 3: Equivalent flexural stiffness for the proposed and RKU models for $H_2 = 10$ mm

	ω_1 (rad/s)	η_1	ω_2 (rad/s)	η_2	ω_3 (rad/s)	η_3
3D model	13372	0.0619	20819	0.0422	24190	0.0499
Proposed model	13652	0.0967	18530	0.0987	21892	0.0993
RKU model	15810	0.0764	21570	0.0782	25569	0.0788

Table 6: Natural frequencies and loss factors of the free plate when $H_2=5$ mm

	ω_1 (rad/s)	η_1	ω_2 (rad/s)	η_2	ω_3 (rad/s)	η_3
3D model	19078	0.0677	29405	0.0497	33090	0.057
Proposed model	18878	0.1242	24807	0.1230	28770	0.1213
RKU model	21990	0.0979	29068	0.0979	33827	0.0970

Table 7: Natural frequencies and loss factors of the free plate when $H_2=10$ mm

not monotonically grow with frequency, the maximum error being a 18 % for the RKU method and 2 % for the proposed formulation and the first mode, but a 4 % and 10 % for the second mode for the RKU method and the proposed formulation respectively. The results follow the same trend and order of magnitude for the third mode as well. This fact can be attributed to the shape of the mode and to the effect the shear deformation has in it.

In this case some of the natural frequencies obtained by the proposed formulation are below the ones for the 3D model contradicting the general trend.

209 The reason is that the 3D model presents modes with coupled in-plane and
 210 out-of-plane deformation making the 3D model stiffer than the plate.

211 *3.1.3. Clamped in one edge*

212 The computed values for the CLD plate when it is clamped in a single edge
 213 for the three values of thickness are shown in Tables 8–10.

	ω_1 (rad/s)	η_1	ω_2 (rad/s)	η_2	ω_3 (rad/s)	η_3
3D model	1680	0.0408	3840	0.0716	9605	0.0486
Proposed model	1695	0.0319	4088	0.0378	9836	0.0430
RKU model	1937	0.0259	4680	0.0303	11308	0.0340

Table 8: Natural frequencies and loss factors of the cantilever plate when $H_2=1$ mm

	ω_1 (rad/s)	η_1	ω_2 (rad/s)	η_2	ω_3 (rad/s)	η_3
3D model	3926	0.0970	8001	0.1171	18343	0.0875
Proposed model	4039	0.0842	9193	0.0932	19777	0.0989
RKU model	4628	0.0652	10594	0.0731	23050	0.0785

Table 9: Natural frequencies and loss factors of the cantilever plate when $H_2=5$ mm

	ω_1 (rad/s)	η_1	ω_2 (rad/s)	η_2	ω_3 (rad/s)	η_3
3D model	5843	0.1259	11097	0.1221	31773	0.0717
Proposed model	6116	0.1163	13190	0.1232	33836	0.1185
RKU model	7011	0.0876	15261	0.0958	39934	0.0952

Table 10: Natural frequencies and loss factors of the cantilever plate when $H_2=10$ mm

214 As in the previous cases, when the CLD plate is clamped in a single edge,
 215 the natural frequencies obtained from the proposed model fall in between the
 216 ones provided by the other two models. This way, the proposed formulation
 217 computes the frequency of the second mode, the one with the biggest error,
 218 with an accuracy of 6 %, 15 % and 19 % for the thin, medium and thick plate
 219 respectively, while the errors of the RKU method are 22 %, 32 % and 38 %.

220 As for the loss factor, the RKU underestimates its value, which implies that
 221 the amplitude of the response predicted by this method would be higher (see
 222 Section 3.3.2).

223 *3.1.4. Simply supported in all edges*

224 The computed natural frequencies and loss factor for the simply supported
 225 plate and the three values of thickness are shown in Tables 11–13. Due to the
 226 symmetry of the plate, the second mode is double.

227 The simply supported case is the one which the proposed model resembles
 228 the most the reference 3D model due to the fact that the mode shape were
 229 supposed to be sinusoidal in the formulation and this assumption holds true

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	ω_1 (rad/s)	η_1	ω_2 (rad/s)	η_2	ω_3 (rad/s)	η_3
3D model	9496	0.0610	20853	0.0426	31036	0.0396
Proposed model	9162	0.0426	21103	0.0473	31459	0.0492
RKU model	10527	0.0337	24480	0.0364	36819	0.0368

Table 11: Natural frequencies and loss factors of the simply supported plate when $H_2=1$ mm

	ω_1 (rad/s)	η_1	ω_2 (rad/s)	η_2	ω_3 (rad/s)	η_3
3D model	18467	0.0932	34836	0.0674	47436	0.0581
Proposed model	18633	0.0987	36547	0.0977	49696	0.0929
RKU model	21692	0.0782	43215	0.0773	59319	0.0728

Table 12: Natural frequencies and loss factors of the simply supported plate when $H_2=5$ mm

	ω_1 (rad/s)	η_1	ω_2 (rad/s)	η_2	ω_3 (rad/s)	η_3
3D model	22901	0.1040	40116	0.0739	53087	0.0608
Proposed model	24930	0.1229	45397	0.1106	59928	0.0999
RKU model	29216	0.0979	53953	0.0893	71706	0.0805

Table 13: Natural frequencies and loss factors of the simply supported plate when $H_2=10$ mm

for a simply supported plate. In this way, the proposed formulation deviates a maximum of 13 % for the third mode and the thickest plate while the RKU has an error of 35 %.

3.2. Mode shapes

In order to verify the ability of the proposed formulation to correctly obtain the modes of the system, the Modal Assurance Criterion (MAC) between the modes shapes of the 2D and 3D model is computed.

For vectors φ_i and φ_j MAC is defined as

$$\text{MAC} = \frac{|\varphi_i^H \varphi_j|^2}{|\varphi_i^H \varphi_i| |\varphi_j^H \varphi_j|}. \quad (20)$$

This way, two identical modes shapes would produce a MAC value of one whereas for two orthogonal ones the value would be zero. For all the boundary conditions considered, the MAC value for the first three modes ranges between 0.7 and 1. The lowest value is related to the symmetric cases, in which the position of the nodal lines is not fixed.

To illustrate this point, in Figures 4–6 the first three bending modes for the thickest cantilever plate and the three models into consideration are shown together with the MAC values obtained. Even if this is the most adverse case because the thick viscoelastic core makes the solid have modes with coupled bending and shear displacement, it can be seen that both plate modes are able to reproduce the behaviour of the structure.

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Figure 4: First mode for the cantilever CLD plate when $H_2 = 10$ mm

Figure 5: Second mode for the cantilever CLD plate when $H_2 = 10$ mm

3.3. Dynamic response

The response of the plate is computed by solving the motion equation in the frequency domain

$$(-\omega^2 \mathbf{M} + \mathbf{K}^*(\omega)) \mathbf{u}^* = \mathbf{F}(\omega) \quad (21)$$

for the response vector \mathbf{u}^* in a frequency range between 0 and 10 kHz and considering 600 samples so that the resolution is acceptable. The force vector $\mathbf{F}(\omega)$ is in this case a uniform impulse pressure on the surface of the plate (1 Pa).

For the comparison between models, the RMS value of the transverse response $\mathbf{u}^*(\omega)$ on the plate surface is used, defined as

$$u_{\text{rms}}(\omega) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N |u_n^*(\omega)|^2} \quad (22)$$

where N is the number of nodes in the model.

In the following sections the response in the frequency domain for the three models and different boundary conditions is analysed. All the cases share some common trends:

- The static response is higher for the 3D model: nor the proposed formulation neither the RKU model account for shear stress in the static case and, thus, these models behave as a thin plate under these conditions.

Figure 6: Third mode for the cantilever CLD plate when $H_2 = 10$ mm

- The RKU model overestimates the value of the resonating frequencies and the amplitude of the peaks.
- The proposed formulation is able to reproduce the results obtained from the 3D model both in terms of frequency and amplitude for all boundary conditions studied. The difference between the two are explained by the effect of the in-plane deformation that is not considered by the proposed formulation.

3.3.1. Clamped in all edges

In Figure 7 the amplitude of the response according to the three models under study is presented.

It can be concluded that, for the clamped plate, the proposed formulation reproduces the response of the 3D model, in terms of resonant frequency and amplitude of the peaks, better than the RKU model, specially for the thinnest plates. When the frequency increases the divergence between the 3D model and the proposed formulation increases as well due to the growing effect of the shear. As for the amplitude, the proposed formulation predicts a lower response because, for this case, it overestimates the value of the loss factor.

3.3.2. Clamped in one edge

In Figure 8 the response of the CLD plate when it is clamped in a single edge is shown.

The proposed formulation gives better results than the RKU also for the plate clamped in a single edge. In this case, as the resonant peaks appear at lower frequencies, the agreement between the 3D and the proposed formulation is greater but deteriorates when the thickness of the viscoelastic layer increases.

3.3.3. Simply supported in all edges

Figure 9 shows the response for the three models when the CLD plate is simply supported in all edges.

The simply supported case is the one that is better represented by the proposed formulation both in terms of resonant frequency and amplitude because,

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Figure 7: Amplitude for the clamped case: (a) $H_2=1$ mm; (b) $H_2=5$ mm; (c) $H_2=10$ mm

as previously stated, in this case the assumptions taken by the proposed formulation are fulfilled. For the rest, the general trends of the other cases apply: the RKU overestimates the frequency of the resonant peaks while the proposed formulation, even if able to compute the frequency of the peaks accurately, slightly underestimates their amplitude, specially at higher frequencies and thick viscoelastic layers.

4. Conclusions

A homogenised formulation to model the dynamic behaviour of CLD plates is proposed and its accuracy compared to the standard formulation used in the field, the RKU model, and a 3D model is tested.

It is shown that the proposed formulation is able to compute both the eigenpairs of the system and the dynamic response more precisely than the RKU with a much lighter computational effort than a 3D model, specially when the viscoelastic core of the CLD plate is thick.

It should be pointed out, however, that as the model does not take into account the in plane deformation, it is only valid to compute the bending modes of the plate, but taking into account that the application of CLD plates is noise

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Figure 8: Amplitude for the cantilever case: (a) $H_2=1$ mm; (b) $H_2=5$ mm; (c) $H_2=10$ mm

reduction and the bending modes are precisely the ones producing noise, this fact cannot be considered a limitation of the formulation.

Also, it is worth noting that, unlike the RKU method, the proposed formulation is valid also for unconstrained layer damping plates. All these mentioned features make the proposed formulation a general method for the dynamic study of surface treatments.

As a final remark, it should be mentioned that, in order to further improve the accuracy of the proposed formulation, it would be necessary to apply a correction factor that depends on the boundary conditions the plate is subjected to.

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960 with the flexural stiffnesses for the layer i following

$$961 \quad D_i = \frac{E_i H_i^3}{12(1 - \nu_i^2)} \quad (B.2)$$

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963 and the rest of the variables defined as

$$964 \quad X^* = \frac{G_2^* S}{k^2 H_2} \quad (B.3)$$

$$965 \quad Y = \frac{12 H_{31}^2}{S(E_1 H_1^3 + E_3 H_3^3)} \quad (B.4)$$

$$966 \quad S = \frac{1}{E_1 H_1} + \frac{1}{E_3 H_3} \quad (B.5)$$

$$967 \quad H_{31} = \frac{H_1 + H_3}{2} + H_2 \quad (B.6)$$

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970 and where k_B stands for the wave number of the bending wave

$$971 \quad k_B = \sqrt[4]{\frac{\omega^2 \rho_S (H_1 + H_2 + H_3)}{D_{eq}}} \quad (B.7)$$

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